

Turkey's Middle East Policy: Vectors, Aims and Results

NATALIIA KHOMA*
(Lviv Polytechnic National University)

YEVHENIIA VOZNIUK**
(Lesya Ukrainka Volyn National University)

Abstract

This article studies Turkey's Middle East policy since its foundation in 1923. Turkey's interest in the Middle East is bound up with a resurgence of the traditional basis of Turkish foreign policy, namely Ottomanism (neo-Ottomanism) and Pan-Turkism (neo-Pan-Turkism). Two periods of Turkey's relations with the Middle East will be examined: 2002–2016, corresponding to the conceptual design and implementation of Davutoğlu's initiatives with the support of the AKP party, and 2016–2020, the post-Davutoğlu era. It will be shown that throughout both periods, Turkey tried to go from being a buffer country to becoming a diplomatically active state and the leader of the Middle East. The country's Middle East policy thus underwent a gradual shift from soft power to a combination of hard and soft power. In the process, Turkey's policy of "zero problems with neighbors" has given way to a new reality of "zero friends." Any current cooperation Turkey has with its neighbors is mostly pragmatic rather than friendly. In the following, it will be shown how the current configuration of Turkey's foreign policy combines neo-Ottomanism and Islamism (Islamist neo-Ottomanism), and that Turkey's interests have extended to parts of the Middle East which have never been under Ottoman rule.

Keywords: Turkey, Middle East, Turkey's Middle East policy, Justice and Development Party (Adalet ve Kalkınma Partisi, AKP), neo-Ottomanism.

Introduction

The Middle East has been plagued by several major conflicts, including the Arab Israeli conflict, hostile relations between Sunni and Shiite forces, and

* Nataliia Khoma is a Professor at the Department of Political Sciences and International Relations, Lviv Polytechnic National University, Ukraine (nataliia.m.khoma@lpnu.ua).

** Yevheniia Vozniuk is an Associate Professor of International Affairs and Regional Studies at the Faculty of International Relations, Lesya Ukrainka Volyn National University (voznjuk.yevhenija@eenu.edu.ua).

the Syrian civil war, which, along with a general lack of democracy and major human rights violations, among other issues, have been drawing attention to the region for a long time. Most Middle Eastern countries have strong geopolitical ambitions and have mainly adopted neo-authoritarian models of governance, which pose a threat to stability both in the region and beyond.

Following the Arab Spring, Middle Eastern countries entered an Arab Winter, which resulted from the rebels' failure to fulfil their initial aspirations through the revolutions. Coalitions with differing interests have rapidly formed in the Middle East since then, which is currently the most conflict-prone region in the world, in a state of what has been aptly described as "stable instability."¹ At the same time, the availability of hydrocarbon resources in the Middle East and its geographical location at the intersection of three continents, among other factors, make this region a crucial subject of international policy.

During its so-called republican period (1923-2002), Turkey paid little attention to the countries that had once been provinces of the Ottoman Empire. The historical trauma of the empire's collapse, especially of the Arab Revolt in 1916-1918, which Turkey refers to as the "Arab betrayal," has left a strong imprint on the collective consciousness, according to Ofra Bengio and Gencer Özcan.² At times, it resonated in republican Turkey's political course. Thus, the new Turkish elite sought to affiliate Turkey with the West and simultaneously dissociate it from the Middle East. At this point in its history, Turkey saw the Middle East as fraught with various complex issues which it preferred not to be entangled in.³

Turkey's ties with the Middle East during the Cold War were particularly strained. For instance, Turkey's relations with Syria and Iraq suffered from territorial disputes over the province of Hatay (currently part of Turkey) and the city of Mosul (currently on Iraqi territory) respectively.⁴ One of the most contentious issues was control over the Tigris-Euphrates River system. Syria

¹ Vadym Volokhov, "Middle East: Stable Instability," Independent Analytical Center for Geopolitical Studies Borysfen Intel (online), October 18, 2019, accessed April 29, 2020, <https://bintel.org.ua/en/analytics/geopolitics/blizkij-sxid-stabilna-nestabilnist/>.

² The military uprising against Ottoman rule in the Arabian Peninsula, which aimed to create a single independent Arab state extending from Syria to Yemen. Ofra Bengio and Gencer Özcan, "Old Grievances, New Fears: Arab Perceptions of Turkey and Its Alignment with Israel," *Middle Eastern Studies* 37, no. 2 (March 2001): 50–92, <https://doi.org/10.1080/714004395>.

³ Malik Mufti, *Daring and Caution in Turkish Strategic Culture: Republic at Sea* (New York: Palgrave Macmillan, 2016).

⁴ Meliha Benli Altunışık and Özlem Tür, "From Distant Neighbors to Partners? Changing Syrian-Turkish Relations," *Security Dialogue* 37, no. 2 (June 2006): 229–248, <https://doi.org/10.1177/09670106060666172>; Nevin Coşar and Sevtap Demirci, "The Mosul Question and the Turkish Republic: Before and After the Frontier Treaty, 1926," *Middle Eastern Studies* 42, no. 1 (January 2006): 123–132, <https://doi.org/10.1080/00263200500399611>.

has repeatedly accused Turkey of monopolizing water resources, notably through attempts to build dams on the two rivers that would cause severe water shortages in Syria and Iraq. In 1998, Turkey's plans to raise a dam on the Euphrates almost sparked a war with Syria. These are just a few examples of Turkey's tense relations with Middle Eastern countries during the Cold War.

Today, Turkey is committed to involving itself in the politics of seven regions clustered around it which are central to Eurasian security, namely Central Europe, the Balkans, the Eastern Mediterranean, the Black Sea region, the Caucasus, the Middle East, and Central Asia. Turkey's geographic position at the crossroads of these regions has given rise to disputes over its status as a regional leader and its intention, reflected by its foreign policy and national security strategies, to exert significant influence over the domestic affairs of Middle Eastern states, as well as in the Balkans, the Caucasus, and Central Asia. On the whole, Turkey's latest foreign policy attests to its ambition to rise from a peripheral to a central position on the international front.

The coming to power of the moderate Islamist Justice and Development Party (*Adalet ve Kalkınma Partisi*, AKP) in 2002 marked a significant departure from the earlier paradigm of Turkish politics.⁵ In terms of foreign policy, the changes had been heralded by Turkish Islamists' long-rooted criticism of the country's policy of indifference toward the Middle East. Islamists similarly frowned upon Turkey's NATO membership, although they had condoned it during the Cold War in order to ward off a communist threat. In the following years, relations between AKP-led Turkey and the Middle East began to intensify. This process was accompanied by the revival of Ottoman ideology (neo-Ottomanism) and Pan-Turkism (neo-Pan-Turkism).

It is clear that through romanticization of its Ottoman past, Turkey is trying to forge a new historical and geographical identity of an Islamist orientation in order to affirm its importance and elevate itself from the status of a buffer country to that of a diplomatically active state and the leader of the Middle East. A number of scholars, such as Hakan Yavuz, Hsan Dai, and Burhanettin Duran, have addressed this issue of Turkey's identity.⁶ Although Turkey has openly declared its aspiration to become the regional leader of the Middle East, this is not a status it could attain in the foreseeable future. The

⁵ Ahmet Sözen, "A Paradigm Shift in Turkish Foreign Policy: Transition and Challenges," *Turkish Studies* 11, no. 1 (March 2010): 103–123, <https://doi.org/10.1080/14683841003747062>.

⁶ M. Hakan Yavuz, *Islamic Political Identity in Turkey* (New York: Oxford University Press, 2003); Hsan D. Dai, "Transformation of Islamic Political Identity in Turkey: Rethinking the West and Westernization," *Turkish Studies* 6, no. 1 (March 2005): 21–37, <https://doi.org/10.1080/1468384042000339302>; Burhanettin Duran, "The Experience of Turkish Islamism: Between Transformation and Impoverishment," *Journal of Balkan and Near Eastern Studies* 12, no. 1 (March 2010): 5–22, <https://doi.org/10.1080/19448950903507313>.

Turkish government's goal to transform the country's status through its foreign policy has so far been mostly fruitless.

Turkey has certainly improved its mutually beneficial, i.e., pragmatic, collaboration with certain Middle Eastern states such as Qatar. However, a number of recent events in the region, including Turkey's 2019-2020 military operations in the north of Syria, code-named Operation Peace Spring, and the deployment of Turkish troops to Libya in early 2020, have engendered new conflicts between Turkey and the Middle East, instead of bringing the country closer to fulfilling its goal of leadership in the region. Factors which aggravate tensions in this conflict-prone region keep emerging and thus attract continuous scholarly attention toward Turkey's Middle East policy, which has already been the subject of extensive academic research.

The aim of this contribution is to characterize the role of contemporary Turkey in the Middle East and to identify the function of neo-Ottomanism in its foreign policy. In particular, an assessment will be made of Turkey's current prospects for leadership in the region and it will be examined whether neo-Ottomanism helps or hinders Turkey in its aspirations. Possible scenarios for Turkey's bilateral relations with certain Middle Eastern countries will also be discussed.

Research Methods

Research was based on role theory in the sense of Kalevi Jaakko Holsti and Chih-yu Shih.⁷ The term "role" refers to the policy pursued by a certain state, such as Turkey, in a particular region, such as the Middle East. Roles determine the purpose and content of individual foreign policies. In Turkey's case, its role reflects its perception of itself as an actor as well as the leader of international relations in the Middle East, in terms of its location, status, and political actions in the context of the social reality of the region. With the theoretical concept of role, greater insight can be gained into Turkey's mission in the Middle East.

Turkey's role was studied both diachronically and synchronically. From a diachronic perspective, it has been shaped by the country's majestic past at the head of the Ottoman Empire, at the time of which its prosperity peaked, and is

⁷ Kalevi Jaakko Holsti, "National Role Conceptions in the Study of Foreign Policy," *International Studies Quarterly* 14, no. 3 (September 1970): 233–309, <https://doi.org/10.2307/3013584>; Chih-yu Shih, "Seeking Common Causal Maps: A Cognitive Approach to International Organization," in *Contending Dramas: A Cognitive Approach to International Organization*, eds. Martha L. Cottam and Chih-yu Shih (New York: Praeger, 1992), 39–56.

oriented toward the bright future promised by neo-Ottomanism, the dream of restoring Turkey's former greatness. From a synchronic perspective, Turkey's role determines its standpoint in international relations and its interactions with other individual countries, which in turn perform their own roles. Consequently, through an analysis of Turkey's bilateral relations with the Middle East, a deeper understanding of Turkey's synchronic role can be gained.

Turkey is trying to project its Ottoman past onto its future by striving to become the leader of the Middle East, and in the long run, a world superpower. In other words, it views current events and its own plans through the lens of the greatness of the Ottoman Empire of which it sees itself as the modern successor. Thus, Turkey is proof that the role that a state has crafted for itself in the past can predetermine the issues it faces in the present day when establishing its identity in the scope of its international relations.

It can be assumed that there is a direct causal relationship between Turkey's fear of remaining a secondary state in the Middle East and its decision to forge a neo-Ottoman identity based on Islamist politics, an ideology which has been opposed by many Middle Eastern states, including the United Arab Emirates (UAE), Saudi Arabia, Egypt, and Bahrain. However, the emergence of Turkey's neo-Ottoman identity is also related to other complex factors including Turkish President Recep Tayyip Erdoğan's neo-authoritarian inclinations and his overt ambition to become the leader of the Muslim world.⁸

If a state is overall satisfied with its current position at the regional or international level, it tends to anchor its national role conception in the present, through active interaction with other countries.⁹ This is not the case with Turkey, which is not only fixated on an idealized past, but has also failed to achieve effective cooperation with the Middle East. At present, there is tension or even direct confrontation between Turkey and most Middle Eastern states, and the relations that are developing between them are mostly of a pragmatic and situational nature, rather than being friendly and durable.

The Ottoman Empire had colonized many Arab populations of the Middle East, and the independent states that have arisen out of it are still suffering from collective trauma. This residue of their colonial past makes them averse to building constructive relations with modern Turkey, whose neo-Ottoman ideology further alienates them. The resulting tension is exacerbated by the policies enforced by Erdoğan and the AKP as a whole, who actively promote narratives about the Ottoman Empire, call for the resumption of Ottoman traditions, and emphasize the need to revive Ottoman values and ideas.

⁸ M. Hakan Yavuz, "Social and Intellectual Origins of Neo-Ottomanism: Searching for a Post-National Vision," *Die Welt des Islams* 56, no. 3-4 (2016): 438-465, <https://doi.org/10.1163/15700607-05634p08>.

⁹ Zalina Balakhova, "National Role Conception in Foreign Policy of a Modern State," *Science and World* 7, no. 35 (2016): 108-110.

Romanticization of the Ottoman Empire continues to influence Turkey's view of its own role in world politics. It is typical in this regard, insofar as nations which once controlled empires are often prone to exaggerating their former glory and favoring politicians who propagate such narratives. Furthermore, the fact that Turkey has been searching for status and overestimating its regional impact in light of its majestic Ottoman past for two decades so far can be taken to suggest that this is in fact its true role in the Middle East, an area characterized by differing geopolitical priorities.

The vast majority of Middle Eastern countries openly denounce Turkey's claims to leadership in the region. Saudi Arabia has even situated Turkey in a so-called "Triangle of Evil," along with Iran and the Islamic State. Overall, Turkey is regarded as a destabilizing rather than integrative factor in the area and could be said to be waging an unofficial cold war with some Middle East countries, including the UAE, Saudi Arabia, Egypt, and Bahrain. Turkey has even managed to elicit further criticism from already antagonistic states, especially from Syria.

The gravity of the issue of Turkey's leadership in the Middle East is evidenced by the fact that the normalization of its relations with individual states has consistently proven problematic. Countries that are opposed to Turkey, spearheaded by Saudi Arabia, are not only unwilling to recognize Turkey's leadership, but they have also been actively imposing manifold restrictions on its regional influence.

It should be borne in mind that in performing its role, any state fears two main risks, that of losing its established role and that of finding a new role but failing to fulfil it. Claiming the role of the leader of the Middle East is essentially Turkey's attempt at resolving the problem of its status in the region. Currently, it is not performing its desired role due to a number of factors, even though leadership in the Middle East is among the core objectives of its foreign policy.

Neo-Ottomanism as the Ideological Basis of Turkey's Middle East Policy

Due to the obstacles to its accession to the European Union (EU), Turkey became increasingly afraid of remaining a secondary state, one which the West values only for the military, strategic, economic, and political benefits it could derive from it, regardless of Turkey's own interests. Consequently, the popularity of efforts to affiliate Turkey with Europe underwent a sharp decline, accompanied by a renewed interest in the traditional foundations of Turkish foreign policy. Ottomanism and Pan-Turkism were thus soon revived.

Neo-ottomanism is not officially enshrined in Turkish legislation. Nevertheless, this term is widely used by experts and scholars to designate Turkey's new Middle East policy, which has its historical roots in the Ottoman Empire (1299-1923). Neo-ottomanism evolved as a concept in the mid-1980s. English historian David Barchard used the term in 1985 to refer to a possible vector of Turkey's development.¹⁰ It was later consolidated in its current sense by Stephanos Constantinides, who used it to describe Turkey's return to a foreign policy model based on imperial traditions and its aspirations to attain the role of a regional leader in the Middle East, as well as in the Balkans, the Caucasus, and Central Asia.¹¹ The specific components of neo-Ottomanism that he posited include a strengthened Islamist component in foreign policy (without necessary prejudice to earlier European aspects), a movement away from Kemalist legacy, and support for Turkish minorities abroad.¹²

Turkish political scientist Hakan Yavuz defines neo-Ottomanism more broadly and considers that its adoption by Turkey represents the formation of a new Turkish identity. The emergence of neo-Ottomanism is a consequence of the social changes that contributed to the rise to power of pro-Islamic elites, as well as the geopolitical changes that took place after the Cold War, among other factors.¹³

According to Hakan Yavuz, the external framework of neo-Ottomanism has a strong ethnic (Turkish) basis, as the Turkish nation is meant to play a central role in the realization of the new imperial project in the Muslim world. The object of Turkish imperial ambitions is first and foremost the Balkans, where the Muslim heritage of the former Ottoman Empire is still preserved. Moreover, Yavuz believes that neo-Ottomanism does not aim to revive Turkey as an Ottoman superpower, but rather to create a new macro-identity to unite the nations which share a common Ottoman and Islamic past.¹⁴

The integration of neo-Ottomanism into Turkey's foreign policy has marked a radical departure from pro-Western Kemalism. Neo-ottomanism was first imputed to Turkish politics by the Greeks in 1974, when Turkey invaded Cyprus.¹⁵ The ideology rejects many Western (neoliberal) values and is based

¹⁰ David Barchard, *Turkey and the West* (London: Routledge & Kegan Paul, 1985).

¹¹ Stephanos Constantinides, "Turkey: The Emergence of a New Foreign Policy; The Neo-Ottoman Imperial Model," *Journal of Political and Military Sociology* 24, no. 2 (Winter 1996): 323–334.

¹² Constantinides, "Turkey," 323.

¹³ M. Hakan Yavuz, "Turkish Identity and Foreign Policy in Flux: The Rise of Neo-Ottomanism," *Critique: Critical Middle Eastern Studies* 7, no. 12 (Spring 1998): 21–22, <https://doi.org/10.1080/10669929808720119>.

¹⁴ Yavuz, "Turkish Identity," 23, 40.

¹⁵ Kemal H. Karpat, "The Civil Rights of the Muslims of the Balkans," in *Studies on Ottoman Social and Political History: Selected Articles and Essays*, ed. Reinhard Schulze (Boston: Brill, 2002), 524.

on the premise that Turkey's interests are not reconcilable with a pro-Western orientation. These points have been highlighted by Yılmaz Çolak and Yavuz.¹⁶

Supporters of neo-Ottomanism among the Turkish establishment often justify their adherence to this ideology in terms of a historical responsibility for the adversities that currently beset countries seen as part of the so-called Ottoman legacy. In particular, according to Turkish neo-Ottoman theorist Ahmet Davutoğlu (former Minister of Foreign Affairs and Prime Minister), Turkey's Ottoman past has placed a burden of geocultural and geopolitical responsibility on the country and has demanded a reformation of Turkish strategic thinking. He also states that a revival of its historical heritage would open up new opportunities for Turkey.¹⁷

The first deviations from Kemalism in Turkish foreign policy became apparent during the administration of Prime Minister Turgut Özal (1983-1989), before the AKP came to power. During his subsequent presidency (1989-1993), Özal proclaimed that the twenty-first century would be "Turkey's century" and the then Prime Minister Süleyman Demirel envisaged a vast Turkish realm extending from the Adriatic all the way to the Great Wall of China, with Turkey as a cultural and historical center which would bind together newly created states, starting with the post-Soviet states of Central Asia.

Although the notion of neo-Ottomanism has been widely applied to Turkey's policy of reviving Ottoman traditions and culture, its meaning and its legitimacy remain debatable. In the literature on the issue of neo-Ottomanism, one can find nationalistic approaches which are critical of it, as well as more moderate assessments that object to the perception of neo-Ottomanism as a continuation of Ottomanism. The controversial nature of the neo-Ottomanism has been rightly noted by Edward Wastnidge, who points to its broad range of interpretations as well as its conceptual difficulties.¹⁸

The active implementation of neo-Ottomanism began after the AKP came to power in Turkey. The party described itself and its supporters as "descendants of the Ottomans" and "the new Ottomans." Although it was established only in 2001, it won the national elections as soon as November 3, 2002, obtaining 363 out of 550 seats in the Grand National Assembly, which indicates that the ideas that it presented in its political program had already been brewing within Turkish society for some time.

¹⁶ Yılmaz Çolak, "Ottomanism vs. Kemalism: Collective Memory and Cultural Pluralism in 1990s Turkey," *Middle Eastern Studies* 42, no. 4 (July 2006): 587–602, <https://doi.org/10.1080/00263200600642274>; Yavuz, "Turkish Identity."

¹⁷ Ahmet Davutoğlu, *Stratejik Derinlik: Türkiye'nin Uluslararası Konumu* [Strategic Depth: Turkey's International Position] (Istanbul: Küre Yayınları, 2001).

¹⁸ Edward Wastnidge, "Imperial Grandeur and Selective Memory: Re-Assessing Neo-Ottomanism in Turkish Foreign and Domestic Politics," *Middle East Critique* 28, no. 1 (2019): 7–28, <https://doi.org/10.1080/19436149.2018.1549232>.

The tenets of Turkish neo-Ottomanism are consanguinity, territory, Ottoman ideology, and language. The principle of consanguinity is applied to the different Turkic peoples, seen as blood brothers of Turks. The principle of territory, in turn, consists of claims to lands formerly under Ottoman rule. It was rejected by Kemal Atatürk, but it has since then been accepted by the current political elite. Closely related to these two principles is the desire of the Turkish establishment to develop a contemporary Ottoman ideology, a macro-identity which would elevate Turkish national identity to the superregional level. Finally, the Turkish language is to be reborn as a lingua franca and efforts have already been undertaken to bring it closer to its obsolete Ottoman form. For instance, Arabic borrowings have been restored after having been eliminated by Turkish linguists in an attempt to reinforce the Turkic basis of the language. It is noteworthy that Arabic has borrowed some words from Turkish too.

Turkey's gradual drift away from the traditions entrenched in the Ottoman period and fundamentalist Islam, as well as its aspirations for integration into Europe as a nation state, have been disrupted in the last two decades. During this period, the country has been actively reintroducing Islam in its politics, increasing its control over society and ceasing pressure on the Islamic clergy, contrary to previous Kemalist practices.

Islamism and neo-Ottomanism are closely interwoven.¹⁹ More specifically, neo-Ottomanism, endorsed by the AKP, is to some extent motivated by Islamist identity.²⁰ Government officials speak with increasing zeal of continuing imperial traditions in present-day Turkey and of the need to revive Ottoman customs and ideology. The primary objective of the political socialization and resocialization of citizens is to instill an imperial mentality.

Neo-ottomanism is based on veneration of the former glory of the Ottoman Empire, which controlled an immense territory in its golden age, spanning three continents. Current neo-Ottoman strategies are aimed at reaffirming Turkey's role in formerly Ottoman-ruled regions, which are viewed as part of Ottoman heritage. In Europe, they include a large part of the Balkan Peninsula, the Ukrainian peninsula of Crimea, the Republic of Cyprus, and the Greek island of Rhodes; in Asia, the countries of the Caucasus and Levant, much of the Arabian Peninsula, modern Iraq, and parts of Iran; and in Africa, northern Algeria, Libya, Tunisia, Egypt, Sudan, and Eritrea.²¹

¹⁹ Ivaylo Hristov, "Neo-Ottomanism: Emergence, Ideology and Political Doctrine," *Social Evolution and History* 18, no. 1 (March 2019): 139–156, <https://doi.org/10.30884/seh/2019.01.08>.

²⁰ Behlül Özkan, "Turkey, Davutoğlu and the Idea of Pan-Islamism," *Survival* 56, no. 4 (August-September 2014): 119–140, <https://doi.org/10.1080/00396338.2014.941570>.

²¹ Ömer Taşpınar, *Turkey's Middle East Policies: Between Neo-Ottomanism and Kemalism*, Carnegie Papers no. 10 (Washington: Carnegie Endowment for International Peace Publications Department, 2008), 15.

There is no consensus among researchers on the reasons, substance, or consequences of the neo-Ottoman course that the Turkish Republic has taken. A number of scholars, including Svante E. Cornell, Blake Hounshell, Joshua E. Keating, and Ömer Taşpınar, describe the recent changes in Turkey's foreign policy as an axis shift aimed at reorienting Turkey toward countries with a Muslim majority, in line with the AKP's ideology.²² Other researchers, such as Tarik H. Oğuzlu, do not concur with this assessment, arguing that neo-Ottomanism is not a means to dissociate Turkey from the West, but rather a pragmatic approach serving to increase Turkey's chances of joining the EU by diversifying its foreign policy vectors in other regions.²³ The AKP's transition from thorough Europeanization to soft Eurasianism is similarly seen by Ziya Öniş and Şuhnaz Yılmaz as consistent with Turkey's traditional tendency to maintain a multi-vector foreign policy.²⁴

The secular-Islamist dichotomy is a leitmotif in Turkish politics and the opposition between the two ideologies could shed light on the reasons for the shift to neo-Ottomanism.²⁵ It has been said that the proclamation of a secular Turkish Republic was not an inevitable outcome of Turkish War of Independence (1919-1923), given that there were many people still loyal to the throne. Since then, different sociopolitical groups have been divided on the subject of the role of religion in politics.

An alternative explanation for Turkey's shift to neo-Ottomanism is that this ideology represents an attempt to expand the country's economic and trade ties.²⁶

²² Svante E. Cornell, "What Drives Turkish Foreign Policy?," *Middle East Quarterly* 19, no. 1 (Winter 2012): 13–24; Blake Hounshell, "Mr. 'Zero Problems'," *Foreign Policy*, November 28, 2010, accessed May 30, 2020, <https://foreignpolicy.com/2010/11/28/mr-zero-problems/>; Joshua E. Keating, "The List: The World's Kissingers," *Foreign Policy*, February 11, 2010, accessed June 19, 2020, <https://foreignpolicy.com/2010/02/11/the-list-the-worlds-kissingers/>; Ömer Taşpınar, "The Rise of Turkish Gaullism: Getting Turkish-American Relations Right," *Insight Turkey* 13, no. 1 (Winter 2011): 11–17.

²³ Tarik H. Oğuzlu, "Middle Easternization of Turkey's Foreign Policy: Does Turkey Dissociate from the West?," *Turkish Studies* 9, no. 1 (March 2008): 3–20, <https://doi.org/10.1080/14683840701813960>.

²⁴ Ziya Öniş and Şuhnaz Yılmaz, "Between Europeanization and Euro-Asianism: Foreign Policy Activism in Turkey during the AKP Era," *Turkish Studies* 10, no. 1 (March 2009): 7–24, <https://doi.org/10.1080/14683840802648562>.

²⁵ Clemens Hoffmann and Can Cemgil, "The (un)Making of the Pax Turca in the Middle East: Understanding the Social Historical Roots of Foreign Policy," *Cambridge Review of International Affairs* 29, no. 4 (2016): 1279–1302, <https://doi.org/10.1080/09557571.2015.1119015>.

²⁶ Kemal Kirişçi, "The Transformation of Turkish Foreign Policy: The Rise of the Trading State," *New Perspectives on Turkey* 40 (2009): 29–57, <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0896634600005203>; Kemal Kirişçi and Neslihan Kaptanoğlu, "The Politics of Trade and Turkish Foreign Policy," *Middle Eastern Studies* 47, no. 5 (September 2011): 705–724, <https://doi.org/10.1080/00263206.2011.613226>; Mustafa Kutlay, "Economy

This theory is plausible considering that the AKP's policy is in essence commercially opportunistic.²⁷ A year before the AKP came to power, Turkey faced one of the biggest financial crises in its history, involving a series of bank failures, a GDP per capita decrease of about 6%, and an increased public debt.²⁸ However, in the first decade of the AKP's governance, the trend was reversed: the market reacted positively to the single-party rule and to the end of a long period of shaky coalition governments.²⁹ Some economic accomplishments, especially in 2002-2012, ensured greater public support for the AKP's policies.³⁰ A key aspect of the economic upturn of that period was the growth of foreign trade. Its total volume soared from \$72 billion in 2001 to 400 billion in 2014. As trade expanded, so did the influence of interest groups (representing big business) on Turkey's foreign policy decisions.³¹ It is no coincidence that large business delegations now often accompany Erdoğan on official visits abroad.

The factors that have shaped Turkey's neo-Ottoman course include the geopolitical situation at the end of the Cold War, which forced Turkey to reconsider its security policy in the face of the rapidly changing circumstances in the Middle East, among other regions. Since Turkey and the United States no longer had a common adversary after the Soviet Union's collapse, they no longer shared a fear of a single existential threat. The United States came to see the rogue states of the Middle East, particularly Iran, Iraq, and Syria, as a threat instead, but Turkey was dependent on them. In fact, its commercial relations with them were prospering. Turkey was therefore wary of any potential disruptions to the stability in the region.

as the 'Practical Hand' of New Turkish Foreign Policy: A Political Economy Explanation," *Insight Turkey* 13, no. 1 (2011): 67–88; Güneş Murat Tezcür and Alexandru Grigorescu, "Activism in Turkish Foreign Policy: Balancing European and Regional Interests," *International Studies Perspectives* 15, no. 3 (August 2014): 257–276, <https://doi.org/10.1111/insp.12004>.

²⁷ Hugh Pope, "Pax Ottomana? The Mixed Success of Turkey's New Foreign Policy," *Foreign Affairs* 89, no. 6 (November-December 2010): 162.

²⁸ Ufuk Demiroğlu, "The Effects of the Investment Decline on Potential GDP in Turkey's 2001 and 2009 Crises," *Central Bank Review* 13, no. 3 (September 2013): 25.

²⁹ Ziya Öniş, "Beyond the 2001 Financial Crisis: The Political Economy of the New Phase of Neo-Liberal Restructuring in Turkey," *Review of International Political Economy* 16, no. 3 (August 2009): 409–432, <https://doi.org/10.1080/09692290802408642>.

³⁰ Refet S. Gürkaynak and Selin Sayek-Böke, "AKP Döneminde Türkiye Ekonomisi" [Turkey's Economy under the AKP], *Birikim* 296 (December 2013): 64–69; Turan Subaşat, "The Political Economy of Turkey's Economic Miracle," *Journal of Balkan and Near Eastern Studies* 16, no. 2 (2014): 137–160, <https://doi.org/10.1080/19448953.2014.910396>.

³¹ Altay Atlı, "Businessmen as Diplomats: The Role of Business Associations in Turkey's Foreign Economic Policy," *Insight Turkey* 13, no. 1 (Winter 2011): 109–128; Kirişçi, "The Transformation."

Davutoğlu based Turkey's new foreign policy on the concept of strategic depth. He believed that the country's separation from the Arab world for decades had been a mistake and that it was time to intensify its strategic depth through fundamental new roles in the Middle East, such as that of "the natural leader" of the region, of a "historical big brother," or of a "protector of Muslim minorities."³² Thus, Turkey undertook the task of increasing its economic, political and cultural presence and influence in the region.

In order for Turkey to regain its role as a regional power and an influential player on the international stage after a long period of inactivity, it feels compelled to embrace and assert its historical and geographical identity. The concept of strategic depth is based on the idea that Turkey cannot pursue a one-dimensional policy in light of its historical and cultural heritage; instead, it must present itself as a central country and affirm its strengths.

Davutoğlu worked on establishing the principle of zero problems with neighbors at the heart of Turkey's foreign policy, rather than neo-Ottomanism. He correctly anticipated that neo-Ottomanism would be perceived as a form of modern expansionism. The then President of the Republic of Turkey, Abdullah Gül (2007-2014), also sought to distance himself from allegations that his country had changed its foreign policy axis.³³ Nevertheless, Turkey's foreign policy became the subject of intense debate. What was at issue was whether Turkey had really moved away from a pro-Western orientation and realigned itself with the Middle East and Asia. In 2009-2010, media across the world were teeming with headlines such as "How the West Lost Turkey" or "Who Lost Turkey?"³⁴ The spotlight was Turkey's transformation from a buffer state to a diplomatically active, multidimensional state.

An example of the expression of neo-Ottomanism as an unofficial principle of Turkey's foreign policy is the doctrine of the "Blue Homeland" (*Mavi Vatan*). This doctrine, which infringes public international law through its violation of official maritime boundaries, seeks to extend Turkey's borders within the Mediterranean. It started with naval exercises conducted under the name of "Blue Homeland" between February and March 2019, and in September of the same

³² Aylin Gürzel, "Turkey's Role as a Regional and Global Player and Its Power Capacity: Turkey's Engagement with Other Emerging States," *Revista de Sociologia e Política* 22, no. 50 (2014): 95–105, <https://doi.org/10.1590/1678-987314225007>.

³³ "Claims of Axis Shift Stem from Ignorance, Bad Intentions, Says Gül," *Today's Zaman* (webpage), June 15, 2010, accessed May 15, 2020, <https://web.archive.org/web/20121006054307/http://www.todayszaman.com/tz-web/news-213148-claims-of-axis-shift-stem-from-ignorance-bad-intentions-says-gul.html>.

³⁴ Nick Danforth, "How the West Lost Turkey," *Foreign Policy* (online), November 25, 2009, accessed June 10, 2020, <https://foreignpolicy.com/2009/11/25/how-the-west-lost-turkey/>; Doug Bandow, "Who Lost Turkey? Not Europe," *Cato Institute*, June 14, 2010, accessed June 10, 2020, <https://www.cato.org/commentary/who-lost-turkey-not-europe>.

year, an inflammatory photograph appeared of Erdoğan posing in front of a redrawn map of Turkey's maritime borders with Greece, bearing the inscription "Turkey – the Blue Homeland."

The concept of the Blue Homeland was first voiced in 2006 by Turkish Admiral Cem Gürdeniz. His vision of Turkey's maritime jurisdiction incorporated large areas of the Black and Mediterranean Seas and left room for the addition of the Persian Gulf and the Red Sea. Thus, the Blue Homeland is not just a romantic nickname for Turkey, but a holistic geopolitical concept that embodies the country's military and political plans for the next decade. Turkey's deployment of troops to Libya in January 2020 can be interpreted as part of the implementation of the Blue Homeland doctrine. An earlier step in this direction was the controversial agreement signed on November 27, 2019, between Erdoğan and Libyan Prime Minister Fayez al-Sarraj, which provided Turkey with access to a section of the Mediterranean rich in hydrocarbon resources that is within the maritime borders of Greece and Cyprus.

The ultimate goal of advocates of neo-Ottomanism was to transform Turkey not only into a regional but also a global power, taking advantage of its history and geographical location. Such a transformation requires an independent foreign policy, not dependence on superpowers. In sum, Turkey must pursue an active diplomatic and economic policy and enhance its international status, but at the same time avoid confrontation with neighboring countries.

In keeping with the theoretical premises of neo-Ottomanism, Turkey seeks to reinforce its influence over post-Ottoman countries primarily through soft power. A popular contemporary instrument of soft power are Turkish historical television series which promote thinly veiled neo-Ottoman ideas.³⁵ However, Turkey's military campaigns in recent years, such as the 2019 offensive into the north of Syria and troop deployments to Iran in 2015 and Libya in 2020, have been characterized by both hard and soft power. It is possible that Turkey is combining the two methods in individual strategies as a form of smart power.

At the Atatürk commemoration ceremony held on November 10, 2016, Erdoğan delivered a speech in which he presented his imperial fantasy, which stands in ironic contrast to Atatürk's own views.³⁶ He declared:

"Turkey is bigger than Turkey, make no mistake. We cannot confine ourselves to 780,000 km². Our physical boundaries are one thing, and the boundaries of our hearts are another.

³⁵ Senem B. Çevik, "Turkish Historical Television Series: Public Broadcasting of Neo-Ottoman Illusions," *Southeast European and Black Sea Studies* 19, no. 2 (2019): 227–242, <https://doi.org/10.1080/14683857.2019.1622288>.

³⁶ Majet Nehme, "Erdoğan's Neo-Ottoman Dreams Was on Libya's Shores," *The Arab Weekly*, January 5, 2020, accessed July 10, <https://thearabweekly.com/erdogans-neo-ottoman-dreams-was-libyas-shores>.

Our brothers in Mosul, Kirkuk, Aleppo, Homs, Misrata, Skopje, Crimea and the Caucasus may very well be outside our borders, but we carry them all in our hearts.”³⁷

These words present Erdoğan as a hyper-nationalist, deeply convinced of Turkey’s duty to maintain ties with its historical territories. His conception of modern Turkey simultaneously draws on neo-Ottomanism and Islamism and therefore instantiates Islamist neo-Ottomanism. Moreover, since his foreign policy entails the use of force for the purposes of domination, it can be considered a modern imperialist policy.

Despite the fact that Turkey refuses the label “neo-Ottomanism,” its current foreign policy betrays its intention to extend and consolidate Turkish supremacy over other states and regions, first and foremost the Middle East. It thus appears that neo-Ottomanism ideally describes the principles of Turkey’s contemporary foreign policy. It has become the ideological basis for the development of a new macro-identity through the use of political, economic, cultural and other forms of influence. Therefore, this article contends that Turkey’s latest geostrategy is Islamist neo-Ottomanism.

However, Turkey’s current foreign policy is also determined by neo-Pan-Turkism. Space constraints preclude a detailed discussion of the latter, but it is important to note that Turkey has established a geostrategic plan for the country’s development by 2023 which foresees a leading role in the world for nations of Turkic origin and ethnicity. Since the 1990s, Turkey has announced its intentions to create a powerful Turkic state within the geographical confines of the former Ottoman Empire but also other areas with a dense Turkish population. At present, the Turkic nations that feature in Turkey’s public discourse are also one of the principal components of its foreign policy.

From the Concept of “Zero Problems with Neighbors” to the Reality of “Zero Neighbors without Problems”

In 2007-2010, Turkey made active efforts to turn the concept of zero problems with neighbors, proposed by Davutoğlu, into a reality, and in 2009, it became the official foreign policy doctrine of the republic. The concept was a revision of traditional Kemalist values in matters of foreign policy and was

³⁷ Recep Tayyip Erdoğan, “10 Kasım Gazi Mustafa Kemal’i Anma Töreninde Yaptıkları Konuşma” [Speech at the Mustafa Kemal Atatürk Commemoration Ceremony, November 10], (speech, November 10, 2016), Presidency of the Republic of Turkey, <https://www.tccb.gov.tr/konusmalar/353/61155/10-kasim-gazi-mustafa-kemali-anma-torende-yaptiklari-konusma>.

aimed at consolidating Turkey's status as a regional leader and turning it into a global power.³⁸

Davutoğlu's approach was based on the supposition that resolving its issues with its neighbors would allow Turkey to focus on dealing with its domestic problems and developing its economy. If Turkey should succeed in fulfilling this goal, it would eventually come to play an important role in Europe, the Middle East, the Caucasus, and Central Asia, aided by its geopolitical position. As a result, Turkey's participation would become indispensable to the resolution of all significant issues in these regions. At first, Turkey's only aim in following the principle of zero problems with neighbors was to simply enhance its relations with neighboring countries, but later on, it resorted to aggressive mechanisms serving to empower it and enable it to steer the course of political processes in the latter.

Following in the footsteps of the previous Turkish Minister of Foreign Affairs, İsmail Cem, Davutoğlu directed the AKP in such a way as to establish good neighborly relations with both Greece and Cyprus.³⁹ In 2009-2010, the AKP also made attempts to stabilize relations with Armenia and mitigate the enmity that had persisted between the two countries since WWI.⁴⁰ Since Turkey was facing a multitude of difficult problems with its neighbors, a successful realization of Davutoğlu's concept seemed inconceivable. However, Turkey subsequently acquired the necessary resources to implement it thanks to the economic boom it experienced.

The concept of zero problems with neighbors quickly evolved into a more ambitious goal to resolve all disputes in which Turkey was directly or indirectly implicated. Attempting to extend its power, Turkey has declared new interests in Africa, the Balkans, and even Latin America and East Asia.⁴¹ It has

³⁸ Hanna Zamikula, "Ahmet Davutoğlu's Foreign Policy Concept: The Main Theoretical Provisions," *Hileya: naukoviy visnyk* 136, no. 9 (2018): 296–301.

³⁹ Ziya Öniş, "Multiple Faces of the 'New' Turkish Foreign Policy: Underlying Dynamics and a Critique," *Insight Turkey* 13, no. 1 (Winter 2011): 47–65; Ziya Öniş and Şuhnaz Yılmaz, "Greek-Turkish Rapprochement: Rhetoric or Reality?," *Political Science Quarterly* 123, no. 1 (2008): 123–149, <https://doi.org/10.1002/j.1538-165X.2008.tb00619.x>.

⁴⁰ Aybars Görgülü, "Towards a Turkish-Armenian Rapprochement?," *Insight Turkey* 11, no. 2 (Spring 2009): 19–29.

⁴¹ Mehmet Özkan, Biril Akgün, "Turkey's Opening to Africa," *The Journal of Modern African Studies* 48, no. 4 (December 2010): 525–546, <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0022278X10000595>; Erhan Türbedar, "Turkey's New Activism in the Western Balkans: Ambitions and Obstacles," *Insight Turkey* 13, no. 3 (2011): 139–159; Murat Önsoy, "Latin America-Turkey Relations: Reaching Out to Distant Shores of the Western Hemisphere," in *Turkish Foreign Policy: International Relations, Legality and Global Reach*, ed. Pınar Gözen Ercan (London: Palgrave Macmillan, 2017), 237–258; Bahadır Pehlivan Türk, "East Asia in Turkish Foreign Policy: Turkey as a

furthermore taken on the role of peacemaker between Israel and Syria, Serbia and Bosnia and Herzegovina, the Fatah and the Hamas in Palestine, Iran and the West, the hostile parties in Somalia, etc.⁴²

Since some of the states with which Ankara sought to resolve all problems had authoritarian regimes, a contradiction arose with the mission that the AKP had defined for itself, namely, to serve as beacon of democratization. This problem became apparent in the summer of 2009, when Iran quelled its rebellious Green Movement. Turkey did not react critically to this repression, unlike many world leaders. Shortly thereafter, Turkish leaders became aware that pushing a policy of “zero problems” could invite accusations of actually working toward “zero problems with dictators.”⁴³

After this realization, Turkish leaders condemned the Assad regime in Syria and became supportive of the Syrian opposition. This was part of the rapid deterioration of relations between Turkey and Syria from 2011 onward. Turkey’s position on the Assad regime reflected the AKP’s intention to present itself as a democratic force capable of putting a stop to military interference in governance. It is noteworthy that in Turkey, the military saw themselves as guardians of Atatürk’s ideals and of secular Turkish nationalism.

Turkey’s foreign policy of zero problems with neighbors temporarily had some positive outcomes, but the Arab Spring and the Syrian Civil War rendered this goal increasingly unfeasible. As Turkey’s ambitions grew, its actual

‘Global Power?’,” in *Turkish Foreign Policy*, ed. Pınar Gözen Ercan (Cham: Palgrave Macmillan, 2017), 259–278.

⁴² Bülent Aras, “Turkey’s Rise in the Greater Middle East: Peace-Building in the Periphery,” *Journal of Balkan and Near Eastern Studies* 11, no. 1 (March 2009): 29–41, <https://doi.org/10.1080/19448950902724380>; Dimitar Bechev, “Turkey in the Balkans: Taking a Broader View,” *Insight Turkey* 14, no. 1 (Winter 2012): 131–146; Meliha Altunışık and Esra Çuhadar, “Turkey’s Search for a Third-Party Role in Arab-Israeli Conflicts: A Neutral Facilitator or a Principal Power Mediator?,” *Mediterranean Politics* 15, no. 3 (November 2010): 371–392, <https://doi.org/10.1080/13629395.2010.517101>; Aylin Gürzel and Eyüp Ersoy, “Turkey and Iran’s Nuclear Program,” *Middle East Policy* 19, no. 1 (Spring 2012): 37–50, <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1475-4967.2012.00521.x>; Pınar Akpınar, “Turkey’s Peacebuilding in Somalia: The Limits of Humanitarian Diplomacy,” *Turkish Studies* 14, no. 4 (2013): 735–757, <https://doi.org/10.1080/14683849.2013.863448>.

⁴³ Mustafa Akyol, “The Problem with Turkey’s ‘Zero Problems’ Plan,” *The New York Times* (online), June 29, 2016, accessed April 27, 2020, <https://www.nytimes.com/roomfordebate/2011/11/15/why-turkey-turned-away-from-syria/the-problem-with-turkeys-zero-problems-plan>.

achievements in terms of foreign policy dwindled.⁴⁴ In fact, most of Turkey's international efforts have been unsuccessful.⁴⁵

It can be assumed that the events of the Arab Spring forced Turkey to shift the focus of its foreign policy from soft to harder power. The practical implementation of such principles as strategic depth, "rhythmic diplomacy," or a "multidimensional foreign policy," promoted by Davutoğlu, proved difficult in the context of the upheaval in the political landscape of the Middle East following the Arab Spring.

Since 2011, Turkey's foreign policy doctrine has been revised in reaction to political transitions and increasing instability in the Middle East. From Davutoğlu's point of view, the revolutions in the Arab countries of the Middle East were natural and inevitable. Turkey had to devise an appropriate strategy to respond to them; thus, the idealism of the principle of zero problems with neighbors was soon tempered by pragmatic reactions to current challenges and a shift towards political interventionism. This idea has been developed by Dutch researcher and politician Marietje Schaake, who believes that the Arab Spring posed a number of obstacles to Turkey's goal of zero problems with neighbors.⁴⁶ Furthermore, the Arab street's calls for respect for human rights draw attention to Turkey's own human right issues.

The realization of the concept of zero problems with neighbors became less effective from 2011 on. At that time, Turkey's relations with Israel grew more strained; new disputes with Cyprus over geological exploration in the Mediterranean arose, in addition to the existing territorial conflict; cross-allegations between Erdoğan and Iraqi Prime Minister Haider al-Abadi intensified; and ties with Iran deteriorated as a result of Turkey's participation in NATO's so-called nuclear shield.

The official website of Turkey's Ministry of Foreign Affairs flaunts the policy of zero problems with neighbors, despite the evident discrepancies between the principle and the observable reality.⁴⁷ Turkish officials have also continued to claim that the vision of zero problems with neighbors is still tenable, yet they had no objection to revising it in response to Turkey's

⁴⁴ Piotr Zalewski, "How Turkey Went from 'Zero Problems' to Zero Friends," *Foreign Policy* (online), August 22, 2013, accessed July 24, 2020, <https://foreignpolicy.com/2013/08/22/how-turkey-went-from-zero-problems-to-zero-friends/>.

⁴⁵ Doğa Ulaş Eralp, *Turkey as a Mediator: Stories of Success and Failure* (Lanham, MD: Lexington Books, 2016).

⁴⁶ Marietje Schaake, "Zero Problems? Time for a New Policy Narrative," *Turkish Policy Quarterly*, June 5, 2011, accessed June 14, 2020, <http://turkishpolicy.com/article/410/zero-problems-time-for-a-new-policy-narrative-spring-2011>.

⁴⁷ "Policy of Zero Problems with Our Neighbors," Republic of Turkey, Ministry of Foreign Affairs, accessed February 3, 2021, <http://www.mfa.gov.tr/policy-of-zero-problems-with-our-neighbors.en.mfa>.

numerous international problems. At this stage, Turkey may well have “zero problems” with different countries’ peoples, but not with their governments.⁴⁸

Researchers have accurately characterized the policy of zero problems with neighbors as idealistic, acknowledging that such an approach is vulnerable to political and economic changes in the region as well as globally.⁴⁹ It is clear that in recent years, the Turkish government has in fact tacitly abandoned it and moved to a foreign policy based on more realistic strategies that protect its national interests. This ambitious policy has led to quite the opposite of what the doctrine of zero problems with neighbors was meant to achieve, and the state that Turkey has found itself in as a result has been termed “precious loneliness.”⁵⁰

The countries with which Turkey sought to resolve all problems eventually realized that this was Turkey’s way of reviving its Ottoman identity. However, they tolerated the policy for some time while they tried to take advantage of the flexibility of the underlying principle to further their national interests. This situation could not be sustained for long as their various conflicts with Turkey intensified. The realization of the concept of zero problems with neighbors, once an ambitious political project, was consequently reduced to a utopian fancy. Thus, Davutoğlu has been derisively called Mr. “Zero Problems,” and in Turkish political discourse, there is more and more talk of the principle of zero problems with neighbors degenerating into a reality of zero friends.

Historical memory and nationalist policies seem to have left not only the Turkish state isolated, but also its citizens, who have an increasingly negative perception of foreign countries, as demonstrated by the results of recent opinion polls, notably the yearly nationwide public polls which Kadir Has University has been conducting on a wide range of domestic and foreign policy issues. In 2019, the countries which were perceived as Turkey’s friends or allies by the largest number of respondents were Azerbaijan (56.5%) and the unrecognized Republic of Northern Cyprus (43.1%).⁵¹ For all countries which had also been covered by the survey in 2018, a decrease was noted in the percentage of respondents who classified them as friends or allies, ranging from -7.1% for

⁴⁸ Ahmet Davutoğlu, “Principles of Turkish Foreign Policy and Regional Political Structuring,” *Turkey Policy Brief Series*, no. 3 (April 2012), accessed July 15, 2020, http://www.ankara.embassy.si/fileadmin/user_upload/dkp_16_van/docs/Principles_of_Turkish_Foreign_Policy_and_Regional_Political_Structuring_by_Ahmet_Davutoglu.pdf.

⁴⁹ Ali Askerov, “Turkey’s ‘Zero Problems with Neighbors’ Policy: Was It Realistic?,” *Contemporary Review of the Middle East* 4, no. 2 (April 2017): 149–167, <https://doi.org/10.1177/2347798917694746>.

⁵⁰ David Gardner, “Turkey’s Foreign Policy of ‘Precious Loneliness’,” *Financial Times* (online), November 16, 2015, accessed May 20, 2020, <https://www.ft.com/content/69662b36-7752-11e5-a95a-27d368e1ddf7>.

⁵¹ Mustafa Aydın (coord.) et al., “Türkiye Eğilimleri: 2019” [Turkey’s trends: 2019], (PowerPoint presentation, Istanbul, Kadir Has Üniversitesi, October 15, 2020) <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.23263.20648>.

Azerbaijan to -22.2% for China, with over -15% for almost half of the countries. No change could be detected in the case of Uzbekistan, Qatar or India, which had not been featured in the 2018 survey. The overall deterioration in Turkish citizens' perception of foreign countries is largely attributable to Turkey's military operations in the north of Syria and the severe condemnation thereof on the part of almost all the countries included in the survey. Specifically, after the start of the Turkish intervention in Syria, world leaders announced potential economic sanctions on Turkey, leaving the Turkish public to feel that everyone was against them, as it were. This sentiment has been observed across all sociodemographic groups in Turkish society. It can be expected that after similar worldwide condemnation of the deployment of Turkish troops to Libya in January 2020, as well as of Turkey's new military operation in Syria, code-named "Operation Spring Shield", at the beginning of March of the same year, the Turkish public will feel even less solidarity with foreign countries.

Turkey's relations with its neighbors and with the Middle East in general, with the exception of Qatar, are considerably strained. Although it has established mutually beneficial partnerships with many countries in the region, these are often based on recent pragmatic interests, which means that any cooperation between Turkey and its neighbors often consists of nothing more than economic relations.

Over the past decade, Turkey has drifted away from the doctrine of Islamic democracy and toward neo-authoritarianism. In so doing, it has alienated itself from its neighbors. However, this does not entirely explain the growing antagonism in its relations with Middle East countries, given that most of them are also have repressive authoritarian regimes in place. It is possible that their hostility towards Turkey is a reaction to Erdoğan's efforts to promote political Islam both domestically and internationally. This brings Turkey closer to Qatar, but leads to friction with many other Arab states, most notably the UAE, Saudi Arabia, Egypt, and Bahrain.

The goal of zero problems with neighbors has in reality thrown up a host of thorny problems of international proportions. Aiming for "zero problems with neighbors," Turkey has ended up with "zero neighbors without problems."⁵² From the very beginning, the implementation of this foreign policy was at odds with its substance, as "zero" was defined too relatively, and "neighbors" too selectively. It is possible the slogan was used to dissemble aspirations to establish a regional hegemony. In any case, Turkey now has almost zero chances of zero problems with its neighbors.

⁵² Christian Makarian, "Turquie: état fort, maillon faible," [Turkey: Strong State, Weak Link] *L'Express* (online), January 19, 2016, accessed July 14, 2020, https://www.lexpress.fr/actualite/monde/europe/turquie-etat-fort-maillonfaible_1754914.html.

Features of Turkey's Middle East Policy

Between 2002 and 2012, the so-called Turkish model was often indicated as a possible pattern of development for the Middle East and the wider Muslim world.⁵³ However, it was revised after the Arab Spring, as the protests and revolutions drove a wedge between Turkey and the Middle East. The political development that benefited Turkey the most was the coming to power of the Muslim Brotherhood, a movement close to the AKP, in Egypt and Tunisia.⁵⁴ However, Turkey's public support for this political organization initially alienated it from most Arab countries and later led to a severe deterioration of political (albeit not necessarily economic) relations with them. All things considered, the Arab Spring could hardly be regarded as a window of opportunities for Turkey; it rather opened a window of vulnerability.

When the civil conflict in Syria escalated into a war and subsequently into a global problem, Turkey was confronted with new challenges, such as the influx of refugees, the upsurge of terrorism, and the cessation of trade through Syria. Turkey's foreign policy also had to grapple with the intensified activity of political organizations that it considers terrorist, in particular the Kurdistan Workers' Party, the unrecognized Islamic State and the Gülenist movement, which would later be suspected of plotting a coup in July 2016. At the same time, Turkish relations with the EU soured. Turkey expected visa-free travel with the EU and a real chance for membership, but instead, the EU accused it of violating liberal democratic principles and imposing restrictions on the civil and political rights of its citizens.

In this section, the main features of Turkey's bilateral cooperation with several Middle Eastern states will be presented. Firstly, the current alliance, i.e., strategic partnership, between Turkey and Qatar is based on a commitment to political Islam and on religious and political forces which fuel it, as well as aims to strengthen both countries' positions in the Gulf region and to form a regional security system. The rapprochement of Turkey and Qatar was facilitated by the emergence of common regional adversaries, primarily Egypt, as the two countries have similar interests in supporting Assad's opponents, as well as the Hamas organization in Palestine. Another contributing factor to cooperation between Turkey and Qatar was the Qatar diplomatic crisis that began in June 2017, when a number of states accused Qatar of destabilizing the Middle East by backing terrorist groups and cooperating with Iran, severed diplomatic relations with it and imposed an economic blockade, cutting off its supplies.

⁵³ The combination of Islam and democracy as well as the transition from a planned to a market economy.

⁵⁴ The Muslim Brotherhood, as the world's leading Islamist political party, won the first post-revolutionary elections in both Tunisia and Egypt. However, their governance did not last long, ending after only a year in Egypt and three years in Tunisia.

Turkey was the first to publicly support Qatar. It condemned the measures taken by the hostile states and lobbied for Qatar's interests on an international scale. The priority components of the alliance between Turkey and Qatar are military cooperation (for example, Turkey has two military bases in in Qatar), trade and mutual investment. On November 26, 2020, Turkey and Qatar signed ten agreements on military cooperation, international trade, free economic zones, and investments.

Thus, Turkey has secured Qatar as an ally, which will enable it to increase its political power in the Middle East, contrary to the interests of neighboring countries, particularly the UAE, Saudi Arabia, and Egypt. Turkey has tried to halt the deterioration of its economic cooperation with the latter, but not always successfully. The relations between the Turkey and Qatar take the form of not only cooperation but also rivalry in certain areas. Naturally, Turkey cannot steer Qatar's foreign policy, which seeks to enhance Qatar's position in the Middle East through its natural resources. The strengthening partnership with Qatar demonstrates that Turkey has now taken an interest in areas that were not under the Ottoman rule historically. The cooperation between Turkey and Qatar is based on strategic rather than colonial relations, and it is for pragmatic reasons that Turkey is reinforcing its cooperation with countries beyond the territorial extent of the former Ottoman Empire. Turkey's approach towards Libya or the north of Syria may be more colonial, but its relations with Qatar are a different matter and show that Turkey has relaxed its neo-Ottoman aspirations by counterbalancing ideological considerations with pragmatic ones.

The first days of 2021 were a turning point in the more than three-year long Qatari crisis. During the 41st Summit of the Cooperation Council for the Arab States of the Gulf held on January 5, 2021, an agreement was reached that resolved the Gulf countries' dispute with Qatar. As a result, the blockade was lifted, and on January 9, 2021, Saudi Arabia reopened its borders to Qatar. At present, it is difficult to predict how Qatar's reconciliation with the Middle East will affect its relations with Turkey. The development is favorable for Qatar, but less so for Turkey, given its tense relations with most Gulf states.

After the AKP came to power in Turkey, relations with Saudi Arabia intensified. The two states were brought closer by a shared desire to curb Iran's growing influence in the region and restrict its control in Syria and Lebanon. Business contacts and investments between the Turkey and Saudi Arabia also increased. However, during the Arab Spring, Turkey and Saudi Arabia supported opposite sides in the revolutions. Their bilateral relations plummeted following the 2013 Egyptian coup and due to their differing attitudes toward the Muslim Brotherhood. The tension was exacerbated by Saudi Arabia's decision in 2017 to boycott Qatar and the assassination of Saudi journalist Jamal Khashoggi in Istanbul in 2018. Saudi Arabia now considers Turkey a part of triangle of evil, along with Iran and the Islamic State. Turkey's military

presence in the north of Syria, its policy toward Cyprus and its continental shelf, and its continued support for Qatar have also fueled Saudi Arabia's antagonism. Finally, Turkey and Saudi Arabia supported opposite sides in the Libyan conflict, and Saudi Arabia has been pursuing a regional policy of driving Turkey out of the Mediterranean zone by strengthening bilateral relations with Cyprus. The political hostility between the two countries has taken a toll on their economic relations too; although the countries remain trade and investment partners, Saudi Arabia's investments in Turkey's economy are on the wane. It appears that Saudi Arabia's goal is to limit Turkey's influence in the region and in the Muslim world through economic leverage.

Within a short time span, cooperation between Turkey and the UAE has also shrunk and the two countries' relations are currently characterized by situational cooperation against the backdrop of aggressive ideological and geopolitical competition. As in the case of Saudi Arabia, the determining factors of this deterioration included Turkey and the UAE's opposing stances on the 2013 Egyptian coup and the Muslim Brotherhood. Turkey and the UAE also differ in their attitudes toward the Qatar crisis, and Turkey's military operations in Syria and Libya and its oil and gas exploration on the continental shelf of the Republic of Cyprus have likewise antagonized the UAE. Finally, the two states have competing interests in the Horn of Africa. The UAE has publicly accused Turkey of "colonial illusions" and of undermining the political interests of Arab states.⁵⁵ The accusation was encapsulated in a Twitter status posted by the UAE Minister of State for Foreign Affairs Anwar Mohammed Gargash, in response to Erdoğan's criticism of the UAE's assessment of the US "Peace Plan" for the Middle East. He declared:

"The low political language of Turkish officials, which has become a feature of their discourse towards the Arab Gulf states and its leaders, is unfortunate. Vocabulary seeks to cover up a reality that cannot be covered, which is that Ankara is the one who interferes in Arab affairs and reproduces colonial illusions that are out of date."⁵⁶

Turkey, in turn, has accused the UAE of involvement in the 2016 attempted coup. Because of this hostility, trade, and investment between the two countries has declined in recent years, and a further surge in their political rivalry is foreseeable.

As for Turkey's relations with Jordan, the two countries have come to an understanding regarding the main regional challenges, such as the Israeli-

⁵⁵ Sylvia Westall, "U.A.E. Accuses Turkey of 'Colonial Illusions' in Arab World," *Bloomberg*, February 2, 2020, accessed June 11, 2020, <https://www.bloomberg.com/news/articles/2020-02-02/u-a-e-accuses-turkey-of-colonial-illusions-in-arab-world>.

⁵⁶ Anwar Gargash (@AnwarGargash), Twitter, February 2, 2020, <https://twitter.com/AnwarGargash/status/1223850764885463040>.

Palestinian conflict, the growing influence of Iran in the region, instability in Iraq and the flow of refugees from Syria. They are also cooperating to strengthen their economic ties and better coordinate their responses to the aforementioned issues. The development of these favorable relations was facilitated by Jordan's resumption of full diplomatic relations with Qatar in the summer of 2019, as well as the fact that Jordan had previously opted out of the Anti-Terror Quartet in 2017, electing to merely reduce its diplomatic representation in Qatar for a while. Turkey and Jordan have also displayed solidarity in their support for Palestine and their consequent criticism of US President Trump's decision to recognize Jerusalem as the capital of Israel.

At the same time, a number of factors have led to some friction between Turkey and Jordan. First of all, Egypt is an ally of Jordan, whereas Turkey's relations with it are very tense. Secondly, Turkey supports the Hamas organization, whereas Jordan endorses their opponent, the Fatah. Thirdly, Turkey has developed cooperation with the Muslim Brotherhood, whereas this movement is opposed to Jordan's King Abdullah II. Fourthly, the terms of the free trade agreement reached by Turkey and Jordan in 2011 proved unfavorable for the latter, which went on to suspend them unilaterally in 2018. Lastly, Jordan is concerned about Turkey's growing power in the Arab world, as it is economically dependent on the monarchies of the Gulf region and keen to strengthen its economic cooperation with them because of its considerable external debt. In general, Jordan is trying to maintain a certain distance in its cooperation with Turkey, as it is highly dependent on foreign aid and therefore eager to keep its relations with the countries of the region as neutral as possible.

Despite the fact that it was the first Muslim state to recognize the State of Israel de jure and establish diplomatic relations with it (in 1949), their relations are another telling example of the transience of partnerships in the Middle East.⁵⁷ Turkey and Israel initially came to an understanding regarding many of their issues with their neighbors and cooperated in the domains of politics, economics, the military and national security. The eventual deterioration of their partnership was brought on by the AKP's policy to intensify cooperation with the Arab countries of the Middle East, as well as the two countries' confrontation over the Palestinian question, since Turkey supports the idea of two states for two nations. The 2010 Israeli raid of the Gaza Freedom Flotilla, which carried humanitarian aid for the Gaza Strip, blocked off by Israel, and the killing of nine activists on the Turkish flagship *Mavi Marmara*, further aggravated Turkey-Israel relations. Afterwards, the two states entered a regional cold war which lasted until the ratification of a reconciliation agreement in 2016. However, their rekindled cooperation was soon compromised by a confrontation over the relocation of the

⁵⁷ Süha Bölükbaşı, "Turkey Copes with Revolutionary Iran," *Journal of South Asian and Middle Eastern Studies* 13, no. 1-2 (Fall/Winter 1989): 102–106.

US Embassy in Israel from Tel Aviv to Jerusalem in May 2018 and the subsequent mass protests with human casualties, as well as the passing of a law that declared Israel a nation-state of the Jewish people in July 2018. In Turkey's view, this law legalized discrimination against Palestinians.

Discourse between Turkey and Israel is dominated by mutual accusations of the use of violence against civilians. At the same time, pragmatic relations such as trade persist between the two countries, against the background of escalating political tension. It should be noted that since Turkey aspires toward leadership in the Muslim world as a non-Arab state, developing ties with the State of Israel is not in its interest, since Israel's very existence is scorned by the Arab states of the Middle East.

Finally, Turkey's relations with Egypt are one of the most problematic issues in the Middle East today. There are many conflicts between the two countries, but so far, they have been prevented from escalating into an armed confrontation. Tensions rose primarily after the 2013 Egyptian coup, which overthrew President Mohamed Morsi, and were later exacerbated by his death on June 17, 2019, the start of the Peace Spring Operation on October 9, 2019, and Turkey's deployment of troops to Libya in 2020, which Egypt denounced. It subsequently conducted military drills on the Egyptian-Libyan border, as a warning for Turkey's benefit. Furthermore, Egypt is antagonized by Turkey's cooperation with Sudan and rumors about Turkey planning to erect a military base on the Sudanese island of Suakin. Finally, gas fields in the Eastern Mediterranean are a point of contention between the two countries, and the Egyptian government has sided with Greece and Cyprus's condemnation of Turkey's illegal maritime operations in Cyprus's exclusive economic zone.

The series of disputes between the two countries presented above has also had repercussions on the political situation in Qatar, Syria, Libya, and the whole Eastern Mediterranean region. Nowadays, the political discourse of both states' leaders is decidedly hostile, and Turkey does not recognize the legitimacy of current Egyptian President Abdel Fattah el-Sisi. Diplomatic relations between Turkey and Egypt are kept to a minimum, involving little beyond the exchange of *chargés d'affaires*. One of the main factors which is still destabilizing their relationship is their disagreement over political Islam. At the same time, economic relations between the two countries have recently gained momentum, although Egypt has called for a boycott of Turkish imports, still under debate, and Turkey's investment projects in Egypt have been suspended.

Conclusions

Turkey's current foreign policy reflects its fear of remaining a minor, buffer state in the shadow of the Ottoman Empire. To restore its former glory,

Turkey has reverted to the traditional foundations of its foreign policy, namely Ottomanism and Pan-Turkism, which stand in stark contrast to pro-Western Kemalism. This shift can be understood in the context of the geopolitics of the post-Cold-War period, the presence of conflicting identities within Turkey, and Turkey's willingness to take responsibility for certain problems (from Turkey's point of view) which afflict post-Ottoman countries in European, Asia and Africa, seen as part of the Ottoman legacy. Turkey has undertaken the task of elevating itself to the status of a superregional power through the revival of political Islam, Ottoman traditions and ideology. At the same time, Turkey is officially denying its neo-Ottomanism in order to ward off accusations of expansionist aspirations. However, Turkey's expansionism is evident both at the doctrinal level, for example, in the Blue Homeland doctrine, and in practice, for example, in Turkey's maritime activity in Greece and Cyprus's exclusive economic zones. Despite Turkey's claims to the contrary, Islamist neo-Ottomanism is now the ideological bedrock of the country's modern foreign policy.

Davutoğlu's doctrine of zero problems with neighbors remains the conceptual basis for Turkey's ambitions to overcome its inferiority in world politics. However, after the events of the Arab Spring, and especially after the attempted coup d'état in Turkey in 2016, Turkey has gone from fostering peaceful cooperation with neighboring countries to recourse to aggressive mechanisms. The outcome of this transition can be treated as a new stage in Turkey's foreign policy in the Post-Davutoğlu Era, a stage characterized by a shift of emphasis from soft to hard methods, in accordance with the principles of Islamist neo-Ottomanism.

The idealistic vision of the doctrine of zero problems with neighbors has come to coexist with Turkey's more pragmatic responses to current challenges and its transformation into an interventionist state. Despite the continual promotion of the doctrine, Turkey has in reality been left with zero friends, with the exception of Qatar, which is interested in partnering with Turkey. Because of the increased aggression of Turkey's foreign policy, other states have accused it of harboring colonial illusions. So far, not only has Turkey failed to reinforce its influence and prestige in the Middle East, due to its support for the Muslim Brotherhood, its military operations in the north of Syria, its deployment of troops to Libya, and other incendiary actions, but most countries in the world have united in opposition against Turkey, even those that are otherwise international rivals.